

JALON

**Regional Energy Community Project
Design
Umbria / Italy**

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Content

<i>1. Context</i>	4
<i>2. Scope of the project design</i>	4
<i>3. Characterization of the region</i>	5
<i>4. Sizing of PV systems</i>	12
<i>5. Financial model</i>	13
<i>6. Business plan</i>	14
<i>7. Legal aspects</i>	17
<i>8. Methodology for engagement</i>	19
<i>9. Conclusions</i>	21

1. Context

EURAC, as the entity responsible for the design of ECs in Umbria, participated in the Calatayud experience to acquire operational and methodological knowledge.

EURAC was able to identify the main challenges and the key changes needed in Italy to establish a supportive local framework that would enable the replication of the Calatayud experience. This was made possible by being kept fully informed at every stage of the project: from participatory processes to identify early adopters, to local training through workshops, to communication and dissemination activities, to regulatory analysis aimed at identifying barriers and strategies for adapting energy community (EC) legislation to rural areas, as well as the exploration of financing models, including public grants.

2. Scope of the project design

JALON aims to develop an innovative approach to facilitate the establishment, growth, and long-term sustainability of ECs, which are designed to address specific social needs of citizens. The project employs a methodology based on close collaboration among local stakeholders. Its focus is primarily on rural areas, where significant obstacles, complex territorial conditions, and particular needs often hinder the pace of the energy transition. Across Europe, numerous factors limit the full potential of ECs, with rural areas facing the greatest challenges. In Umbria, these difficulties similarly act as barriers, which this project seeks to overcome.

Rural areas in Umbria face a structural crisis linked to depopulation and demographic aging, aggravated by the infrastructural and digital isolation of its inland areas. Small-scale family farms suffer from low profitability, high operating costs, and a difficult generational turnover, which encourages land abandonment. While tourism remains a resource, its strong seasonality and concentration in a few destinations put pressure on local resources. ECs may be a powerful tool to help rural Umbria grow, turning electricity costs into a shared benefit. By producing and sharing their own energy, small farms and local residents can significantly lower their bills, which helps fight poverty and stops people from leaving the villages. Installing solar panels on the roofs a new way to earn money without using up good soil for crops and at the same time, it makes these remote areas more independent. Within this project, a specific case study is first identified, serving as the reference point for analysis and experimentation. The energy consumption of the selected site is carefully characterized to gain a detailed understanding of actual needs and electricity demand patterns. Based on this analysis, photovoltaic generation systems solutions are designed to meet the energy demand within a framework of sharing and cooperation within the energy community.

In parallel, the project develops a financial model and a business plan, essential tools to assess the economic feasibility of the initiative, ensure long-term sustainability, and attract potential investors or partners. Furthermore, the most appropriate legal form for

the establishment of the Energy Community is analyzed and defined, providing a clear regulatory framework aligned with strategic and operational objectives.

Finally, particular attention is given to the social and participatory dimension: a methodology is designed to actively engage the local population and raise awareness of the environmental, economic, and social benefits of the energy transition.

3. *Characterization of the region*

Umbria is located in Central Italy, bordered by Tuscany, Marche, and Lazio, covering an area of approximately 8,464 km². About 13% of the region is designated as protected land, and is dominated by rolling hills and the Apennine Mountains, resulting in a relatively low population density. As of January 1, 2025, Umbria had a population of about 851,954 inhabitants¹, with an average density of around 100 inhabitants per km². However, population distribution across the 92 municipalities is uneven: while the main hubs of Perugia and Terni concentrate most residents, rural and mountainous areas face significant depopulation². Figure 1 illustrates the population distribution, and Figure 2, shows the population density across the municipalities of Umbria.

¹ [Istat, demografia in cifre](#)

² [Umbria in cifre, La popolazione in Umbria al 1° gennaio 2025. \(2025\)](#)

Figure 1: Population distribution in Umbria. Source ASTAT

Figure 2: Population density by municipality in Umbria. Source ASTAT

Social and economic issues in rural areas

In Umbria, the territorial classification follows the national methodology based on population density and productive structure, dividing the region into two main rural macro-areas that cover the entire regional surface. Intermediate rural areas represent the most significant portion of the territory, accounting for 70% of the surface area and hosting 84% of the population across 68 municipalities; despite being more populated than mountainous zones, their population density remains well below the OECD threshold of 150 inhabitants per km². Rural areas with comprehensive development problems consist of 24 municipalities covering approximately 30% of the regional territory, characterized by an extremely low population density and home to only 16% of the regional population. In summary, as shown by the Rural Development Program 2014-2020 for the region³, Umbria exhibits a widespread and uniform rural character.

³ [Regione Umbria, Programma di sviluppo rurale 2014-2022](#)

JALON's objectives are closely aligned with regional priorities, including intensifying environmental protection and climate action, revitalizing the socio-economic fabric of rural areas, and fostering the sharing of knowledge and innovation.

These goals take shape through the 2023-2027 CAP Strategic Plan (PSP), the Rural Development Complement (CSR) ⁴ for Umbria. This regional strategy focuses on diversifying income opportunities for agricultural enterprises to boost employment, providing essential services to the local population and enhancing the appeal and accessibility of rural areas.

Known as the "Green Heart" of Italy, Umbria boasts natural heritage and historic villages, as it offers exceptional urban green space, and low land consumption. Moreover, regional renewable electricity production remains significantly higher than levels in Central Italy.

However, as highlighted by Agenzia Umbria Ricerche⁵, these strengths are threatened by a demographic decline sharper than the national average, a trend affecting both urban centres and rural areas. This social fragility is compounded by heavy infrastructural challenges, such as a water network with high losses and insufficient internet coverage.

To address this crisis, a shift toward network economies is essential, reintroducing services to local territories through multifunctional spaces and robust collaboration between public entities and the third sector.

This structural evolution requires the involvement of citizens as co-producers and co-investors of local services. This participatory approach overcomes the limitations of rigid organizations, enabling them to intercept social changes and adapt to the community's true needs. Actively engaging users allows for the redesign of welfare services, transforming territorial management into a driver of resilience and development.

While Umbria remains more resilient than the national average concerning housing costs and poverty levels, over a third of families report significant difficulties with public transport connections. The 2023–2027 CAP Strategic Plan represents a transformative challenge, aiming to evolve rural areas into technologically advanced and diversified "Smart Villages" where living in the rural areas becomes a competitive and sustainable choice. A manifestation of this concept is found in Energy Communities (ECs) which currently stand as the most successful and widely adopted model for turning the Smart Village vision into a functional reality.

⁴ [Regione Umbria, Complemento di sviluppo rurale per l'Umbria 2023-2027](#)

⁵ [Agenzia Umbria Ricerche, L'Umbria in prospettiva futura. Proposte, riflessioni, analisi. \(2021\)](#)

Energy communities

This section examines active ECs in Umbria, which according to Agenzia Umbria Ricerche⁶, may transform consumers into prosumers through democratic participation. While individual impacts are marginal, the collective scale provides significant value across urban and rural landscapes. By replacing centralized models with productive autonomy, ECs redefine the community-territory bond, turning decentralized production into a driver for territorial renewal and a catalyst for the energy transition in fragile areas.

Italy defines seven possible configurations for distributed self-consumption and ECs, but at present, but only three are designed for sharing renewable energy and are therefore subsidised with public funds:

1. Renewable Energy Communities (CER)

This configuration enables the virtual sharing of electricity produced from renewable sources among community members. Energy is shared via the national distribution grid among producers and consumers connected to the same primary substation.

2. Collective Self-Consumption Groups (AAC)

This model involves at least two separate entities—either end-users or producers—each with its own connection point. All participants must be located within the same building or condominium. Generation systems may be installed either in the same building or in other facilities under the full control of the users, as long as they are within the same primary substation area.

3. Individual Remote Self-Consumers Using the Distribution Grid (AAD)

This configuration applies to a single end-user who virtually consumes renewable electricity generated by systems located in areas they fully control. Energy is accessed via that user's withdrawal points connected to the public distribution grid.

The following Table 1 is an overview of energy configurations as of September 2025, in Umbria and officially recognized by the GSE⁷.

⁶ [Agenzia Umbria Ricerche, La transizione energetica in Umbria \(2023\)](#)

⁷ [The GSE \(Gestore dei Servizi Energetici\) is the Italian Energy Services Operator, responsible for promoting sustainable energy production and energy efficiency.](#)

Table 1: Overview of Energy Community configurations in Umbria recognized by GSE

ID	Configuration	Installed capacity (kWp)	RES systems	Members	Municipality
1	CER Via Dei Partigiani	9.75	1	4	Marsciano (PG)
2	CER Ponte Felcino	107.8	1	3	Perugia
3	CER Gubbio-Castiglione (ass.)	999	1	41	Gubbio (PG)
4	CER Nera-Tevere	5	1	24	Narni (TR)
5	CER Del Trasimeno (Coop.)	199.75	1	9	Castiglione del Lago (PG)
6	CER Gubbio 1	26	4	9	Gubbio (PG)
7	CER Alto Orvietano (Coop.)	16	2	12	Parrano (TR)
8	CER Italia Rinnovabile (Coop.)	17	1	10	Orvieto (TR)
9	AAD	89.32	1	2	Perugia
10	AAD	100	1	1	Montefalco (PG)
11	AAD	19.44	1	12	Campello sul Clitunno (PG)
12	AAD	6	1	2	Orvieto (TR)
13	AAD	6	1	4	Orvieto (TR)
14	AAC	11.1	2	2	Marsciano (PG)
15	AAC	9.25	1	7	Narni (TR)
16	AAC	6	1	2	San Giustino (PG)
17	AAC	14	3	3	Perugia

Figure 3 maps Umbria’s Energy Communities (ECs) alongside municipal boundaries to identify those served by the same primary substation.

Figure 3: Map of primary substations and energy communities in Umbria

Identification of key stakeholders

The following stakeholders have been identified in the region.

Energy Communities stakeholders:

- CER Nera-Tevere: established in April 2022, it subsequently expanded to cover the three primary substations serving the municipalities of Narni, Stroncone, and Amelia - <https://cer-narni.it/>
- Cer del Trasimeno : a cooperative founded in 2022 that involves schools, families, associations, and local energy producers - <https://certrasimeno.it/>
- Comunità Enegetica Alto Orvietano: established in 2022; membership is open to all electricity users within the municipalities of Alleronia, Fabro, Ficulle, Montegabbione, Monteleone, Parrano, and San Casciano - <https://cerao.it/>

Social stakeholders:

- Legacoop Umbria: protects and promotes cooperatives by providing specialized consulting and technical assistance to its members - <https://www.legacoopumbria.coop/>

- Confcooperative Umbria: represents cooperative interests to public and political bodies, manages audits, and fosters the creation and growth of new cooperative enterprises - <https://www.umbria.confcooperative.it/>

Technical stakeholders:

- Green Zone: a regional EC operating across Umbria by establishing local clusters mapped to the service areas of primary substations - <https://www.cnaumbria.it/>
- ITS Umbria Academy: a polytechnic academy providing advanced technical and digital training which also prepares technicians in energy system management to optimize efficiency and drive the ecological transition - <https://www.itsumbria.it/>

Public bodies:

- Arpa Umbria: a public agency providing technical-scientific support to regional authorities for pollution prevention, environmental protection, and public health - <https://www.arpa.umbria.it/>

4. Sizing of PV systems

This section outlines the methodological approach used to size photovoltaic systems and analyze the associated energy flows.

The energy assets of the community are owned by the individual members who install them. Energy is first used to meet each owner's self-consumption, with any surplus shared across the community. However, the sizing of these installations is optimized for the EC as a whole, not just for individual users, so while some systems may exceed a single owner's needs, they are efficient and balanced within the broader community context.

The analysis relies on a RECTool⁸, a model designed by EURAC for ECs and adapted to the Italian context, which adopts a bottom-up structure and uses linear programming techniques, with a one-year time horizon and a static framework.

The RECTool is employed to perform a techno-economic-environmental assessment of the EC and to optimize its configuration, providing estimates of the system's energy, economic, and environmental impacts. The model is implemented through oemof⁹, which allows constraints and objective functions to be expressed as linear formulations solved through linear programming.

The analysis has two main objectives:

⁸ [Casalicchio, V., Manzolini, G., Prina, M. G., & Moser, D. \(2022\). From investment optimization to fair benefit distribution in renewable energy community modelling. Applied Energy, 310, 118447. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.118447](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2021.118447)

⁹ [oemof \(Open Energy Modelling Framework\) is an open-source Python-based framework designed for the modelling and optimisation of energy systems.](https://www.oemof.org/)

- optimizing, by considering also economies of scale, the installed capacity of photovoltaic systems (subject to maximum installable limits, where applicable) and battery storage;
- optimizing the dispatch of energy resources within the EC, while minimizing the costs.

The cost components considered include capital and operational expenditures (CAPEX and OPEX), energy-related costs (electricity bills, incentives, revenues from energy sold to the grid), and any tax deductions or similar benefits.

To clarify the energy-cost structure represented in the model, a definition of shared energy is needed: shared electricity is calculated hourly for all connection points linked to the same primary substation and is defined as the minimum between the electricity injected and the electricity withdrawn for sharing purposes.

The following section provides a brief overview of the incentives and cost components relevant to ECs as there are the following support mechanisms designed to promote their development:

- compensation for shared electricity, provided through the reimbursement of specific tariff components (ARERA Resolution 727/2022/R/eel¹⁰).
- premium tariff for shared electricity, established by the CACER Decree¹¹. This tariff consists of a fixed component, linked to the size of the installation, and a variable component that depends on the market price of electricity. An additional premium is applied to photovoltaic systems located in Central Italy and Northern Italy to compensate for their lower productivity compared to installations in Southern Italy. The premium is granted by the GSE for 20 years from the commissioning date of each renewable energy plant. A 50% tax deduction for building renovations¹² can be combined with capital grants.
- compensation for the electricity withdrawal into the grid provided by the GSE¹³.

5. *Financial model*

The financing of an EC can be structured in different ways, depending on its ownership model and the type of partners involved.

Energy plants may be directly owned by the CER, allowing the community to manage production and revenues autonomously, or they may be owned by third parties - either public or private entities - that make the generated energy available for sharing within the community.

¹⁰ [Delibera 727/2022/R/EEL dell’Autorità di Regolazione per Energia Reti e Ambiente](#)

¹¹ [Decreto del Ministero dell’Ambiente e della Sicurezza Energetica del 7 dicembre 2023, n. 414](#)

¹² [Article 16-bis of Presidential Decree 917/1986, letter h](#)

¹³ [Decreto Legislativo 8 novembre 2021, n. 199](#)

For a small-to-medium scale EC in Italy, the most realistic and sustainable financing structure combines private investments by individual members with tax incentives (50% tax deduction available to eligible residential prosumers).

This financial model is proposed in combination with revenues from shared electricity, including the premium tariff for shared energy and compensation for electricity injected into the grid, ensuring both economic viability and member participation.

6. Business plan

The business plan has been developed to guarantee the EC's long-term financial sustainability and overall viability. It is based on key factors such as revenue streams, capital investments, operating costs, and financial and tax-related expenses.

To cover administrative, technical, and operational expenses, the EC charges its members an annual fee. Consumers pay a fixed fee of €25 per year, while prosumers and producers pay an annual fee ranging from €50 to €500, depending on the size of their installed PV system.

Table 2: Input data on savings and revenues used in the Business Plan

Savings / incomes	Unit	Value
Remuneration for the electricity injected into the grid	€/kWh	≈ 0.092
Savings from physical self-consumption	€/kWh	≈ 0.24
Premium tariff for shared energy	€/kWh	≈ 0.111
Compensation of tariff components	€/kWh	≈ 0.011

Table 3: Investment and costs input data deployed in the Business Plan

Investments / costs	Unit	Value
Investment for plant construction	€/kWp	≈ 1100 – 1600 *
Operation and maintenance costs	€/kWp/year	≈ 15 – 20 *
Platform management costs	€/year	2500
Administrative management costs	€/year	6500

Other operating costs	€/year	15000
* For PV systems with a capacity ranging from 6 to 150 kWp		

The EC examined in this study covers two separate primary substations. As a result, each substation represents a distinct energy configuration, and the amount of shared energy eligible for incentives must be determined separately for each configuration.

In total, the community includes 75 consumers and 7 producers, distributed across the two configurations as follows:

- configuration 1: cabin A - 32 connection points (3 prosumers, 29 consumers), including facilities such as a school, gym, kindergarten, library, museum, theatre, church, office, restaurant, canteen, retail store, bookshop, and residential units.
- configuration 2: cabin B - 50 connection points (4 prosumers, 46 consumers), including a winery production facility, a hospital, a swimming pool, an agritourism facility, retail outlets, a nursing home, a shopping center, a supermarket, a pharmacy, and 40 residential households.

Cabin	Type	Consumption (kWh/year)	Category	Max capacity (kWp)
A	School	79569	prosumer	164
	Gym	189600	prosumer	80
	Kindergarten	53046	consumer	-
	Library	20640	consumer	-
	Museum	68800	consumer	-
	Theatre	20000	consumer	-
	Church	16800	consumer	-
	Office	98534	consumer	-
	Restaurant	26000	consumer	-
	Cafeteria	17000	consumer	-
	Retail Store	3640	consumer	-
	Bookstore	4654	consumer	-
	1 residential household	4060	prosumers	6
	19 residential households	68671	consumers	-
B	Olive Oil Mill	28800	prosumer	40
	Hospital	635664	prosumer	250
	Swimming Pool	45967	consumer	20
	Agritourism Facility	20750	consumer	18
	Retail Store	5027	consumer	-
	Olive Oil Mill	31160	consumer	-
	Supermarket	157200	consumer	-
	Nursing Home	126000	consumer	-
	Shopping Center	12773	consumer	-
	Pharmacy	8410	prosumers	-
	40 residential households	144208	consumers	-

This section presents the optimization results, covering energy flows, economic returns, and environmental impacts, across three distinct categories:

1. technical data, such as installed PV capacity, energy production, consumption and self-consumption, grid feed-in, shared energy;
2. economic data, such as investment cost, savings from energy self-consumption, incentives, revenue, O&M costs;
3. identified KPIs, such as share of Self-consumption, Self-sufficiency, CO₂ avoided, NPV over 25 years, Internal Rate of Return, payback period.

Table 4: Technical data of the Business Plan

Parameter	Unit	Configuration 1 (Cabin A)	Configuration 2 (Cabin B)
Installed PV capacity	kWp	182	273
Estimated annual production	MWh/year	253,847	381,567
Aggregated consumption	kWh/year	671,015	1,215,959
Self-consumption	kWh/year	101,078	248,245
Energy fed into the grid	kWh/year	152,769	133,322
of which shared energy	%	83	84

Table 5: Economic data of the Business Plan

Parameter	Unit	Configuration 1 (Cabin A)	Configuration 2 (Cabin B)
Initial investment	€	205,728	309,096
Bill savings	€/year	24,206	59,274
Incentive for shared energy	€/year	16,736	14,833
Energy sold to the grid	€/year	14,764	12,838
Operation & Maintenance	€/year	3,637	5,460
Annual operating costs (platform + administrative costs)	€/year	24,000	

Table 6: Identified KPIs of the Business Plan

Parameter	Unit	Configuration 1 (Cabin A)	Configuration 2 (Cabin B)
Self consumption (physical+virtual)	%	93	
Self sufficiency	%	31	
CO ₂ avoided	t/year	49	78
NPV - 25 years (with bonus 50%)	€	322,081	657,154
IRR	%	14	
Payback period	year	6	

Notes on the results:

- battery storage was excluded by the optimization due to its high investment costs.
- the two system configurations were optimized under a constraint on the maximum installable PV capacity. While the second configuration fully exploits the maximum allowable capacity, the first utilizes only 73% of the installable capacity. Furthermore, from the perspective of the EC, rather than that of the individual member, it is not economically advantageous to install a residential PV system, even when technically feasible.
- annual operating costs are allocated among the configurations proportionally to the share of incentivized energy, although other allocation methods could be used. For the first year, the initial operating cost is considered 15% higher than in subsequent years to account for startup expenses.
- starting from the 21st year, incentives for shared energy are no longer provided, in accordance with current regulations.
- as incentivized energy exceeds 55% of total energy fed into the grid, proceeds go to non-business members or are reinvested for local social purposes.

7. Legal aspects

RECs are often initially constituted as associations, with the intention of subsequently obtaining legal personality or converting into a cooperative as the community expands, both in terms of membership and number of energy installations.

The most selected configuration for the EC is a non-profit cooperative, as it ensures democratic governance, clear separation of assets, fiscal benefits, and the possibility of

distributing economic benefits to members, making it particularly suitable for larger ECs aiming for structured management and benefit sharing.

The EC may include a variety of members, such as natural persons, as well as public and local bodies. Small and medium-sized enterprises (including those partially owned by public authorities) may join only if their main business activity is not the production or sale of energy, while large enterprises are not eligible to become members.

Other eligible participants include associations, foundations, religious organizations, Third Sector Entities (ETS), consortia, and research or training institutions.

The management structure consists of:

1. Assemblea dei Soci (General Assembly) – the sovereign body of the cooperative.

It approves the financial statements, appoints and revokes the members of the Board of Directors and the Auditors, determines their remuneration, and approves internal regulations and statutory amendments.

2. Consiglio di Amministrazione (Board of Directors) – composed of 3 to 9 members, it oversees both the ordinary and extraordinary management of the cooperative. It prepares operational plans and development strategies, defines the economic and financial policies, and may delegate specific functions to one or more directors.

The President of the Consiglio di Amministrazione legally represents the cooperative.

3. Collegio Sindacale (Board of Statutory Auditors) – elected by the Assemblea dei Soci, it ensures compliance with the law and the bylaws, supervises management, and certifies the accuracy of the social report. The task of statutory auditing (revisione legale dei conti) may be assigned either to the Collegio or to an external auditor.

The establishment and ongoing management of the EC require the following documentation:

1. Atto costitutivo (Deed of Incorporation) – specifying the founding members;
2. Statuto (By-laws) – defining the internal governance structure and voting rights;
3. Regole di ripartizione (Benefit distribution rules) – establishing the criteria for the allocation of incentives among members;
4. Contratto tariffa premio GSE (GSE Premium - Tariff Agreement) – to be executed within 90 days from the commissioning of the installations;
5. Contratto di vendita dell'energia (Energy Sale Agreement) – governing the injection of produced energy into the public grid;
6. Contratti di servizio (Service Agreements) – covering production, maintenance, administrative and IT management of the EC.

Any party wishing to be admitted as a member must submit a written application to the Board of Directors, containing the following information:

If the applicant is a natural person:

1. Full name, residence, date and place of birth, contact number, Italian Tax Identification Number, and certified e-mail;
2. Identification codes and point of delivery, indicating their location and specifying whether the applicant is a consumer or prosumer;
3. Details of the production plants or portions thereof whose energy injected into the grid (and not self-consumed) contributes to the EC's shared energy calculation, if the applicant is a producer or prosumer;
4. A copy of the most recent electricity bill for estimating annual consumption (if not otherwise accessible through institutional channels);
5. The amount of capital proposed for subscription, within the by-laws limits;
6. A declaration of full knowledge and acceptance of the current by-laws, internal regulations, and resolutions legally adopted by the corporate bodies;
7. An express and separate declaration of acceptance of the arbitration clause contained in the Statuto and confirmation of having examined the rules of the Camera Arbitrale e di Conciliazione della Cooperazione¹⁴.

If the applicant is a company, association, or other entity:

1. Legal name or denomination, legal form, registered office, contact number, Tax Identification Number, VAT number, and certified e-mail address;
2. For enterprises, the prevalent *codice ATECO* of their economic activity and a declaration stating that participation in the Cooperative as an EC does not constitute their principal commercial or industrial activity;
3. The resolution of the competent corporate body authorizing the application;
4. Identification of the signatory and their legal authority to represent the applicant;
5. For enterprises, a declaration attesting to their qualification as an SME.

8. *Methodology for engagement*

The EC of the Calatayud Region (CERCA), developed within the framework of the European JALON project, has carried out a series of citizen engagement activities targeting residents, associations, and local administrations. Through meetings with residents of various municipalities and training workshops, CERCA has presented the

¹⁴ Body providing alternative dispute resolution services (arbitration and conciliation) for cooperatives.

benefits of sustainable energy and provided technical, economic, and legal information on ECs. Additional training days have been planned to extend engagement to associations, private individuals, and businesses.

Given the success of this methodology, it is suggested that the same approach based on JALON's results be adopted for replication in Umbria. By combining informative workshops, direct community involvement, and tailored outreach strategies, this approach has proven effective in raising awareness, fostering participation, and ensuring that ECs are integrated successfully into local social and economic contexts.

Since the region already hosts active and successful configurations, engagement activities could be further strengthened by demonstrating the feasibility of local energy systems through showcasing real, operational examples, such as existing shared photovoltaic installations and already-implemented community energy projects.

9. Conclusions

The EC in Umbria proposed in this design is summarised below:

- Size of the EC (number of participants), of which:
 - Primary cabins: 2
 - Citizens: 60 households
 - Local shops / commercial 8
 - Industries / production / agriculture 3
 - Local councils / public services 12

- Type and number of self-consumption PV systems:
 - Industrial / production / agriculture PV systems: 2 PV installations without storage, with a total power of 58 kWp.
 - Local councils and public services PV systems: 4 PV installations without storage, with a total power of 397 kWp.

Total: **6 PV installations** without storage, with a total power output of **455 kWp**.

The 6 installations produce **635 MWh** of energy annually.

- Needed investment and funding for:
 - Phase 1: EC set-up (Year 0):
 - Platform, administrative, other operating costs. Non-repayable public funding. **€27,600**.
 - Phase 2: Development of PV projects (Years 1–25):
 - 100% from investments of participant prosumers **€514,824**
 - Platform, administrative, other operating costs. Non-repayable public funding. **€24,000**.
 - compensation for shared electricity, (ARERA Resolution 727/2022/R/eel¹⁰) + premium tariff for shared electricity (CACER Decree¹¹) + compensation for the electricity withdrawal **€59,172**

- REC structure:
 - Legal: non-profit cooperative
 - Electricity suppliers (free choice)
 - Resources:
 - Staff: 2/4 volunteers (free-time),
 - PV system maintenance service.
 - administrator/financial service

- Business plan:
 - The EC charges fees to project participants:
 - EC consumer membership fee: **€25**
 - EC prosumer/producer membership fee: **€50 - €500** (according to PV size)

These figures generate a positive cash flow after 6 years. Over a period of 25 years, this represents an **IRR of 14%**, which ensures the financial sustainability of the EC.

In line with the objectives of the Jalon project, an energy community characterized by a strong social vocation and services closely linked to the local area was analyzed. The energy community (EC) is comprised of 6 photovoltaic installations located in commercial buildings, small industries and public facilities, with a total installed capacity of 455 kWp. Although primarily designed for self-consumption and lacking storage systems, the overall production of the plants and the sharing of energy among EC members generate an annual cash flow of approximately €59,000. After deducting O&M, technical and administrative costs, estimated between €27,000 and €29,000 per year, the investment in the installations is recovered in six years, subsequently enabling the EC to allocate the generated resources to local social initiatives.

During the engagement phase and various meetings with citizens, the design of the EC is aligned with the CACER decree, which stipulates that the community's revenues are to be allocated to social purposes and to the activation or enhancement of local services for the population. Technical and economic simulations also highlight the long-term financial sustainability of the energy community, emphasizing that it is an entity in continuous evolution.

A noteworthy outcome to highlight is that the technical and economic optimization of the energy community resulted in the exclusion of the 6 kWp residential small installation. In this project, from the perspective of the ECe, it is more advantageous for the residential user to remain a pure consumer rather than a prosumer. Ultimately, this result stems from a holistic approach that achieves a more balanced and efficient community configuration. By optimizing not only energy flows but also the strategic allocation of investments, this project delivers a non-trivial solution that maximizes the overall value for the Energy Community.